

Poem

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Introduction by the Author

The poems are about the climate crisis and the ongoing impact of climate on sentient beings, humans and life at large. Water is an elixir of life but we have been polluting it without fail. The poems are ringing the alarm bell about the lurking danger. They talk about how our inventions are the cause of our destruction. They are about how media highlights the world's glam and fame and completely sidelines the cause and effect of the environment at large.

Water

Life, elixir, essence
Patience, persistence
Precious
Water

71 % of the earth
60 % of the body
1 % to drink
50 % wastage
0.003 % left

Water
No water, no life
No sight of delight
No earth, no we

We are all water.
Water is our link.
Water is our soul.

Fresh water, salt water,
Hard water, soft water,
Black water, grey water,
Spring water, tap water,
Distilled water, well water,
Rain water, ground water...

Water, water nowhere, nor a drop to drink.
Water gives life,
Water inhabits lives.

Water

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Because we have invented plastic...

Garbage is what remains when the good, fruitful, valuable, nourishing, and useful has been taken. –John Scanlan

Because we have invented plastic...
Because we want to pollute the river....
Because we want to clog water....
Because we want to choke the gutter....
Because we can't decompose it....
Because we want to pollute the air....
Because we want to poison animals...
Because we want to degrade the land...
Because we want to create slime....
Because we want to have cancer...
Because we want to eat venom....
Because we want to boil the earth....
Because we want holes in the ozone....
Because we want to increase the temperature....
Because we want the earth to decay....

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